

Caricature Classification Using Convolutional Neural Networks

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Abstract - We propose a solution to classify caricatures of various artists according to their unique artistic styles by applying convolutional neural networks on the images of caricatures. We used pretrained models VGG16, ResNet50 and InceptionV3 to extract features from images. Then, we trained ANN's to predict caricaturist names for given images. Our models are able to predict the artists with 95% accuracies on test data.

Index Terms - caricature, computer vision, multi-class image classification, convolutional neural networks, transfer learning

I. INTRODUCTION

Art is an area that humankind was interested in since their existence. Although it includes lots of subjective properties, it is open to be examined by computational techniques. To address as a sub-category, caricatures are examples of artistic works that reveals distinctive style characteristics to identify its caricaturist. Therefore, if it is possible to classify a specific caricaturist's work by looking at the features such as drawing of facial contours, shapes of human bodies and text font.

In this paper, we present a convolutional neural network-based solution that classifies the caricatures of different artists depending on the features extracted from 10 gigabytes of image data. Firstly, as the preprocessing step, we use transfer learning method to extract features from raw data by using creditworthy convolutional neural networks. Then, we train CNNs to classify those caricatures according to their artists.

The main contributions of this work are as follows:

- Our solution proves feasibility of classifying the caricatures by using transfer learning and convolutional neural networks.
- We provide a labeled and preprocessed caricature dataset to be used in related works in the future.

II. RELATED WORK

Fragmentation of an image into meaningful parts for a faster and more accurate learning has been a problem for many. For caricature classification, an algorithm shall focus mainly on catching details that tell on the artists rather than the contents or the context of the caricature. A related work is performed by Saleh and Elgammal (2015), using the paintings extracted from Wikiart as dataset. Performing image classification by style, artist and genre considering the high-

level CNN features and low-level GIST features. Later a related work on image classification using CNN is performed by Balakrishnan, T., Rosston, S., & Tang, E. (n.d.). focused on transfer learning by fine-tuning ResNet and pre-trained VGG models, achieving a test accuracy above 90%.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Problem Definition

Every caricaturist has a unique drawing style because each caricature can be considered as an art form which reflects the characteristics of its creator, in this case, the caricaturist. Although the caricatures of same artist have similar features with respect to shapes, contours and colors used in images, most of the time it is hard for people who are not experienced and do not have enough knowledge about the comic world (popular caricatures, comic works), to recognize the creator of the image. In addition to that, even though each caricaturist has a unique style, there may be cases in which several caricaturists can be affected and inspired by each other. Then, the classification process becomes a complicated task even for an experienced comic reader.

B. Dataset

Raw dataset was formed by collecting caricatures of several caricaturists from the internet and ill-conditioned images were cropped in a way in which they were made suitable to capture the characteristics of the caricature only. We selected 10 classes in total to perform classification where each class represents one caricaturist who may have local reputation (only popular in Turkey), worldwide reputation or both. Each class contains around 500 images, therefore there are approximately 5,000 images in total.

C. Preprocessing

In preprocessing phase, we decided to use 3 pre-trained convolutional neural networks to perform feature extraction on raw dataset and compare the performances of different feature extraction methods at the end. These networks are ResNet50, VGG16 and InceptionV3, namely. The reason that we chose to use convnets is they are much more capable of extracting features and semantic information from images when compared to other deep neural networks. All of these 3 networks are trained on ImageNet dataset and final weights

are frozen to use in future works, which is called transfer learning. Using transfer learning in feature extraction stage helped us to save huge amount of time and energy and increased the reliability of the classification process pipeline.

D. Network Architecture

We implemented an ANN which takes extracted features as input and classify them among 10 different classes as output in one-hot encoded vector form. Then, we completed the classification phase just by selecting classes which correspond to generated output vector. To find out the optimal model, we constructed different network architectures and adjusted network parameters in accordance.

IV. EXPERIMENTS

In this section, we present our experiments and their results. In our work, total of 108 model configurations are experimented separately. These model configurations are formed by using all combinations of different optimizers, hidden layers and epoch counts. We choose RMSprop, Adam and SGD as model optimizers, 3 hidden layer formations and 4 different epoch counts (10, 25, 50 and 100). Hidden layer formations are as follows;

- H0: No hidden layer
- H1: One hidden layer with 128 units
- H2: Two hidden layers with 512 and 32 units

The tables below show the accuracy results of the experiments on the validation set with 3 pretrained models by different epochs, optimizers and hidden layer configurations.

Table 1: VGG16 accuracy results for different configurations

VGG16			Hidden Layers		
			H0	H1	H2
EPOCHS	10	RMSProp	0.19	0.10	0.10
		Adam	0.39	0.38	0.10
		SGD	0.19	0.91	0.87
	25	RMSProp	0.10	0.10	0.11
		Adam	0.33	0.10	0.10
		SGD	0.20	0.20	0.91
	50	RMSProp	0.10	0.10	0.10
		Adam	0.27	0.26	0.20
		SGD	0.85	0.19	0.91

In Table 1, it can be easily observed that VGG16 model is not a good fit for caricature classification task. There are only a few results that are acceptable for an accurate classifier. VGG16 performs better when there are multiple hidden layers because its input size is larger (4096 dim) compared to other two models and it needs more abstraction layers. One can clearly see that SGD optimizer has the best performance among all.

Table 2: ResNet50 accuracy results for different configurations

ResNet50			Hidden Layers		
			H0	H1	H2
EPOCHS	10	RMSProp	0.95	0.95	0.11
		Adam	0.96	0.93	0.94
		SGD	0.95	0.96	0.95
	25	RMSProp	0.96	0.96	0.96
		Adam	0.78	0.97	0.96
		SGD	0.96	0.96	0.96
	50	RMSProp	0.96	0.96	0.97
		Adam	0.97	0.96	0.96
		SGD	0.97	0.96	0.97

In Table 2, almost all accuracy results are similar and over 95%. This indicates that the ResNet50 model is a perfect fit for caricature classification task.

Table 3: INCEPTIONV3 accuracy results for different configurations

INCEPTIONV3			Hidden Layers		
			H0	H1	H2
EPOCHS	10	RMSProp	0.86	0.85	0.11
		Adam	0.90	0.90	0.86
		SGD	0.85	0.86	0.83
	25	RMSProp	0.91	0.91	0.79
		Adam	0.90	0.92	0.87
		SGD	0.90	0.90	0.87
	50	RMSProp	0.92	0.87	0.91
		Adam	0.93	0.93	0.92
		SGD	0.91	0.92	0.91

In table 3, we can observe that the best accuracy results are obtained when using Adam as model optimizer in InceptionV3 model, however, results are lower than ResNet50 model.

As a summary, worst results are acquired with using VGG16 whereas InceptionV3 model has significantly higher accuracy values. Best results are obtained using ResNet50 amongst three different pretrained models.

Best model is selected considering candidate models with different configurations and its corresponding test set accuracy results, because their validation set results were quite similar (96%). To conclude, the best model is obtained by using SGD as optimizer, consisting of ResNet pretrained model and one hidden layer, trained for 50 epochs.

V. RESULTS

In this section, we present the performance metrics of our best model. Model performs with 97% accuracy on validation set while performs with 95% accuracy on test set.

Figure 1: Accuracy plot for our best model

In Figure 1, accuracy versus epoch counts of model training for train and validation sets are illustrated. The model overfits after iteration number 50, by applying the elbow rule, 50 epochs is selected for best model. Hence the model accuracy on validation set approximates to 95%. In Figure 2 below, the loss of train and validation versus epoch counts of model is illustrated.

Figure 2: Loss plot for our best model

In Figure 3, the confusion matrix of our best model is demonstrated. We can observe almost all of our test instances located on the diagonal as expected. The other performance metrics are listed below to verify the reliability of the model.

Table 4: Performance metrics for our best model

Classes (Caricaturists)	Precision	Recall	F1-score
Adam Zyglis	0.99	0.95	0.97
Hassan Bleibel	0.99	0.93	0.96
Kaan Ertem	1.00	0.97	0.99
Mark Streeter	0.96	1.00	0.98
Nate Beeler	0.90	0.96	0.93
Paresh Nath	0.96	0.96	0.96
Serkan Altunigne	1.00	0.95	0.97
Ugur Gursoy	0.93	0.99	0.96
Umut Sarikaya	0.97	0.95	0.96
Yigit Ozgur	0.97	1.00	0.99
Micro Avg	0.97	0.97	0.97
Macro Avg	0.97	0.97	0.97
Weighted Avg	0.97	0.97	0.97

Figure 3: Confusion Matrix for our best model

According to the results with less epoch count of the same model, some test instances of Umut Sarikaya cannot be classified correctly and misclassified as Kaan Ertem. This is well illustrated in the confusion matrix of model that used ResNet pretrained model. Accuracy of this model is roughly 80% which means that apart from the misclassification of these two caricaturists, model has an acceptable accuracy rate. This may have several reasons, a little search on Wikipedia yields the result of a criticism of Kaan Ertem on Umut Sarikaya's authenticity.

Figure 4: Confusion Matrix of misclassified

VI. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we present a machine learning study on classifying the artists of caricatures. Our predictions are based on the image dataset of 10 different caricaturists crawled from web resources. According to the experiments, our models have accuracy over 95%. Our work also stands as a proof of concept approach to apply machine learning methods on artworks since it demonstrates successful results by detecting the discriminative properties of different artists.

In order to do exhaustive experiments for developing models further, the dataset may be enlarged by including more caricaturists. Models developed in the scope of this project may also be used on different types of visual artworks.

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